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Perceived Impact Of Entrepreneurship Education As A Tool For Job Creation, Poverty Reduction And National Development In Katsina State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the perceived impact of entrepreneurship education as a tool for job creation, poverty reduction, and national development in Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The study population comprised 420 entrepreneurs who graduated from six business apprenticeship training centers (BATCs) in Katsina state and graduates of the Business Education Department, Federal College of Education, Katsina, from the 2022/2023 academic session. A stratified sampling technique was used to select samples. A sample size of 201 graduates was used as determined by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The research instrument used was a structured questionnaire developed for this study. The instrument was validated by experts, and its reliability was determined using Cronbach 's alpha ($\alpha = 0.81$). Two hypotheses guided this study. Data gathered from the questionnaire were analyzed using regression analysis at a 5% significance level. The results of the study revealed that entrepreneurship education had a significant impact: H1 and H2 is Strong, with regression weights of 0.739 [$p < 0.001$] and 0.730 [$p < 0.001$], respectively, on job creation, poverty reduction, and national development in Nigeria, and graduates from BATCs acquired more entrepreneurial skills than graduates from the Federal College of Education, Katsina, due to greater engagement in practical training. The study thus concluded that entrepreneurship education plays a crucial role in job creation, poverty reduction, and national development. The study recommends that the government should introduce entrepreneurship training centers in the Colleges of Education in Nigeria for practical skill acquisition among students, provide adequate funds and equipment for the operation of the training centers, and ensure that both students of BATCs and Colleges of Education have access to loans, financial assistance, or equipment for enterprise development after graduating.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education; Job creation; Poverty reduction; National Development

INTRODUCTION

Education has been identified as the engine of national development. It plays a crucial role in social well-being, job creation, poverty reduction, and improvement of people's living standards. Efe (2014) posited that education is a vital tool in the training and development of human resources in any country by

imparting essential skills, capacities, values, knowledge, and attitudes that can be utilized in the transformation of individuals, communities, nations, and the world at large. According to Maina (2013), education serves as a crucial instrument for national development. Facilitating the economic potential of individuals enables them to actively engage in and derive benefits from their nation's economy. Additionally, education facilitates economic growth and fosters transformation by providing a foundation.

In contrast, entrepreneurship education focuses on equipping young individuals with the necessary skills, competencies, knowledge, and traits to become innovative and establish and manage their own businesses. This form of education not only promotes job creation, poverty alleviation, and national development but also contributes to economic growth. The primary objective of entrepreneurship education is to enhance entrepreneurial self-efficacy, self-employment, and risk-taking behavior among potential entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship education creates enormous business opportunities and trains people with innovative enterprise skills to grasp opportunities for starting new entrepreneurial activities (Cheng & Chan, 2009). In addition, entrepreneurship education has various benefits for individuals and nations. This will provide young graduates with adequate training that will enable them to be creative and innovative in identifying great business opportunities. It will also offer functional education to youth to enable them to be well-empowered and self-reliant people in their own right and serve as catalysts for economic growth and development. In addition, it offers tertiary institution graduates adequate training in risk management to make learning outcomes feasible and reduce the high rates of poverty, insecurity, and violence.

Entrepreneurship education will not only foster economic growth but also create employment opportunities for citizens and reduce migration from rural areas to urban centers. This will lead to sustainable development and provide young graduates with the necessary skills and support to establish successful small and medium-sized businesses. By incubating a spirit of perseverance in both youth and adults, entrepreneurship education enables individuals to persist in their business ventures and facilitates a smooth transition from traditional to modern industrial economies. Additionally, entrepreneurship education has been shown to be an effective means of poverty reduction, because economic growth over time is crucial for reducing poverty levels. Entrepreneurship boosts economic growth, enhances educational attainment, and increases the economic growth rate (Mitra and Abubakar, 2011). Entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in changing students' views on becoming self-employed. This is because entrepreneurship education is meant to train students upon graduation to become self-reliant and employers of labor through creative and innovative thinking in identifying new business opportunities (Kamar et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurship education offers numerous advantages for both individuals and nations. It equips young graduates with the necessary skills to identify and seize business opportunities while also providing functional education to empower and make youths self-reliant, serving as catalysts for economic growth and development. Moreover, it offers tertiary institution graduates risk management training to make learning outcomes feasible and to reduce poverty, insecurity, and violence. This study explores the perceived impact of entrepreneurship education as a tool for job creation, poverty reduction, and national development in Nigeria.

Statement Of The Problem

The intended outcomes of entrepreneurship education appear to fall short, as young people and graduates are unable to become self-employed after completing their studies despite the skills and career choices they have acquired through entrepreneurship courses. Akpochafo & Alika (2018). The issue of entrepreneurship education is not related to the curriculum, educational investment, or lack of qualified personnel. Instead, many pointed to educational management as the root cause, including insufficient policy analysis to prepare students for societal integration. The solution does not rely on government initiatives, but on the innovative management skills of educational leaders to transform education into a foundation for job creation, self-sufficiency, crime reduction, socio-economic empowerment, prosperity, and national security. This approach aims to achieve sustainable national development by enhancing access to high-quality practical entrepreneurship education across all levels. Adedayo et al, (2023). It has

been noted that graduates from universities, colleges of education, and technical schools often join the ranks of the unemployed, despite the inclusion of entrepreneurship education in their curricula, which was designed to promote self-reliance (Mohammed et al., 2014). As this goal remains unmet, it is crucial to examine the effects of entrepreneurship education as a means of generating employment, alleviating poverty, and fostering national development in Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The general objective of this study is to examine the perceived impact of Entrepreneurship Education as a tool for job creation, poverty reduction, and National Development in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aimed at the following:

1. To investigate whether entrepreneurship education has effect on job creation for National Development in Nigeria
2. To determine the impact of entrepreneurship education on poverty reduction for National Development in Nigeria
3. To examine the strategies for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education toward National Development in Nigeria

Research Question

1. To what extent does Entrepreneurship Education effected job creation for National Development in Nigeria?
2. How does entrepreneurship education impact on poverty reduction for National Development in Nigeria?
3. What are the strategies for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education toward National Development?

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis one:

H₀₁: Entrepreneurship Education not effected Job creation for national development in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

H₀₂: Entrepreneurship Education not impacted poverty reduction for national development in Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education involves developing attitudes, behaviors, and capacities at the individual level. It is also about the application of these skills and attitudes that can take many forms during an individual's career, creating a range of long-term benefits to society and the economy (Efe, 2014). According to Aliu (2014:4), Entrepreneurship Education is learning directed towards developing in young people those skills, competencies, understandings, and attributes that equip them to be innovative and train them to identify, create, initiate, and successfully manage personal and/or community business and work opportunities, including working for themselves. Akudolu (2010) asserts that the major goal of entrepreneurship education is to promote creativity, innovation, and self-employment among citizens through the inculcation of entrepreneurial knowledge, competencies, and attitudes in learners.

Job Creation

Ayorinde et al (2017) opined that "Job Creation" is the notion that jobs are provided in response to some sort of event or situation. This can be seen when people engage in meaningful activities that can help them fend for themselves and their immediate families in a society that can bring about the physical and economic development of a nation.

Poverty Reduction

Poverty encompasses various aspects including insufficient income, limited assets, lack of skills and confidence, disempowerment, and scarcity of national currency. It can also refer to deficiencies in understanding, culture, or spirit (Singer 2006). Households experiencing financial constraints and a lack of entrepreneurial incentives may face low productivity, leading to poverty (Adenutsi, 2009). According to the World Bank, the major contributors to poverty include political instability, inadequate infrastructure development, ineffective national policies and structural adjustments, and insufficient

investment (Misango and Ongiti, 2013). Commonly, poverty is defined as living on income below a specific minimum threshold. The World Bank classifies individuals living on less than US\$2 per day as impoverished, while those subsisting on less than US\$1.25 daily are considered to be in extreme poverty on a global scale (Chen and Ravallion, 2008).

National Development

According to UNESCO (2000), the ability of a country to improve the social welfare of the people, for example, by providing social amenities such as quality education, potable water, transportation infrastructure, and medical care, goes far beyond the provision of social amenities. This explains why we submit that this definition falls short of the total picture because it tends to ignore the economic components of the developmental process. National development is about the improvement of all spheres of human endeavor that ultimately ensure sustained welfare for citizens of any society (Eferakeya and Ifurueze, 2016). This means that to achieve national development, job opportunities and poverty reduction within the community should be available. Umoren et al. (2018) opined that national development is a function of the development of individuals and corporate entities within a country. National Development, in a broad sense, includes general development in communities, towns, cities, states, and nations as a whole in the best interests of its people. A country can improve its human capital, economy, social welfare, democracy, buildings, national defenses, and other key sectors of national life. National Development refers to the ability of a country to improve the socioeconomic welfare of its people by providing social amenities like good education, clean pipe-borne water, good roads, electricity, transport, and communication Uchenna and Uju, (2020).

Literature Review

In recent years, entrepreneurship education has gained significant attention as a potential tool for job creation, poverty reduction, and national development. It has been widely recognized that entrepreneurship plays a vital role in driving economic growth and creating employment opportunities (Radebe, 2019). The impact of entrepreneurship education on poverty alleviation in Nigeria has been highlighted as significant, contributing to economic growth, job creation, and the development of entrepreneurial skills (Drenket and Gotip, 2018). According to Efe (2014), entrepreneurship education is a solution to unemployment, poverty, and national insecurity by equipping individuals with the skills and knowledge necessary to create opportunities. Maina (2013) asserted that entrepreneurship education in Nigeria has the potential to achieve national development goals, reduce unemployment, and alleviate poverty. Hussain and Bhuiyan (2014) posited that entrepreneurship development is a key tool for stimulating employment and reducing poverty. Mani (2017) argues that changes are needed in the learning process to promote entrepreneurship, and that entrepreneurship should be associated with creativity and change. Lack of experience and funding were identified as major deterrents to starting a business immediately after college. In line with these findings, we recommend more practical skills. Uchenna and Uju, (2020) affirm that entrepreneurship education is a veritable and practical option to remedy the consequences of the global economic implosions and put the nation on the path of national development. Eferakeya and Ifurueze (2016) opine that the entrepreneurship education curriculum is inadequate, lecturers teaching entrepreneurship education are not adequate in number and competence, and they are not well funded.

Theoretical Review

The Need for Achievement Theory (NAT)

This theory shows the functional relationship between the need for achievement, economic development, and entrepreneurial activities. According to McClelland (1956), entrepreneurial activity is a potent process through which the need for achievement leads to economic growth. He further opines that one would expect a relatively greater amount of entrepreneurial activities in a society if the average level of need achievement is relatively high among people (Eferakeya and Ifurueze, 2016).

Risk Taking Theory

According to Alam and Hossan (2003), this theory sees entrepreneurship is mental education that stimulates individuals to take moderate or calculated risks for which they stand to enjoy streams of benefits. This makes people take greater risks in contending with great responsibilities. The theory underscores that entrepreneurship education improves the ability, capability, and potential of a nation’s human capital to undertake risks for which all stand to benefit immensely (Sofoluwe et al,2013).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of 300 youth who graduated from six business apprenticeships Training Centres (BATC) in Katsina State and 120 students who graduated from the Department of Business Education, Federal College of Education, Katsina 2022/2023 session. This resulted in 420 graduates. The sample size of this study was 201, as determined by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Graduates were selected using stratified sampling. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire developed for the study. A structured questionnaire with a four-point rating scale was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument has been validated by an expert. The instrument was pilot-tested on 30 respondents. Data collected from the pilot study were subjected to statistical analysis using test-retest, and its reliability was determined using Cronbach ’s alpha ($\alpha = 0.81$), which showed that the instrument was reliable for the study. Data gathered from the questionnaires were analyzed using regression analysis.

The questionnaires were distributed to the target respondents, and Eighty (180) copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and subjected to statistical analysis, where a mean score of 2.5 and more was considered as an index for acceptance, while regression analysis was used to test the two (2) research hypotheses. All null hypotheses were tested and rejected at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

RESULTS

The followings are the results of the findings and interpretations of this study.

Research Question one: *To what extent does Entrepreneurship Education has effect on job creation for National Development in Nigeria?*

Table 1: The extent to which Entrepreneurship Education has effect on job creation

Opinion	N	Total score	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision rule	Decision
Agree	132	428	2.8	1.3	$2.8 > 2.5$	Agreed
Disagree	60	108				
Total	192	536				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 answers research question one. The table showed that, 132 respondents with a total score of 428, had the opinion that Entrepreneurship Education has a significant effect on job creation for national development. Sixty respondents with a total score of 108 were of the view that Entrepreneurship Education had no significant effect on job creation for national development. Therefore, the results show that Entrepreneurship Education has a significant effect on job creation for national development because the mean score (2.8) is greater than the 2.5 bench mark for agreement.

Research Question two: *How does entrepreneurship education impact on poverty reduction for National Development in Nigeria?*

Table 2: The extent to which Entrepreneurship Education has impact on poverty reduction

Opinion	N	Total score	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision rule	Decision
Agree	129	418	2.7	1.3	$2.7 > 2.5$	Agreed
Disagree	63	107				
Total	192	525				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 answered research question two on how does entrepreneurship education impact on poverty reduction for National Development. The table revealed that Entrepreneurship Education has significant impact on poverty reduction for national development. This is because the mean score (2.7) is greater than the 2.5 bench mark for agreement.

Research Question three: *What are the strategies for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education toward National Development?*

Table 3: The extent to what are the strategies for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education for National Development

S/N	Items	Agree	Disagree	X	SD
1	Provision of funds by Government, financial institution and NGO's	182	10	3.6	1.8
2	Provision of interest free loan to start up business	176	16	3.5	1.7
3	Establishment of centers for Entrepreneurship development	179	13	3.5	1.7
4	Provision of conducive environment and facilities for teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education	169	23	3.4	1.6
Grand Mean				3.5	1.7

Source: field Survey, 2024

Table 3 answered research question three on what are the strategies for enhancing Entrepreneurship Education toward National Development. The table revealed that, Provision of funds by Government, financial institution and NGO's, provision of interest free loan to start up business, establishment of centers for Entrepreneurship development and provision of conducive environment and facilities for teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education will enhance Entrepreneurship Education for national development. This is because the mean score (3.6, 3.5, 3.5, and 3.4 respectively) with grand mean 3.5, is greater than the 2.5 bench mark for agreement.

Null hypothesis one: There is no significant effect between Entrepreneurship Education and Job creation for national development in Nigeria.

Table 4: Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on job creation for national development

Model	B	Std.Err	t.	R-crit	R-cal	R ²	adjustedR ²	Sig
Est. center for Entr.	17.724	.434	5.272	.088	.739	.058	.057	.000
Job creation	.236	.232	1.437					

Source: field Survey, 2024

Table 4 presents regression analysis of the effect of Entrepreneurship Education on job creation for national development. From the table, the computation indicated a calculated r value of 0.739 greater than the critical r value of 0.088 at 0.05 level of significance (p<0.001). The result indicated that, Entrepreneurship Education has significant effect on job creation. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant effect between Entrepreneurship Education and Job creation for national development in Nigeria was rejected.

Null hypothesis one: There is no significant impact between Entrepreneurship Education and poverty reduction for national development in Nigeria.

Table 5: Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on poverty reduction for national development

Model	B	Std.Err	t.	R-crit	R-cal	R ²	adjustedR ²	Sig
Prov. of free Interest loan	19.624	.454	5.973	.088	.730	.052	.049	.000
Poverty Reduction	.421	.232	1.657					

Source: field Survey, 2024

Table 4 presents regression analysis of the impact of Entrepreneurship Education on poverty reduction for national development. From the table, the computation indicated a calculated r value of 0.730 greater than the critical r value of 0.088 at 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.001$). The result indicated that, Entrepreneurship Education has significant impact on poverty reduction. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant impact between Entrepreneurship Education and poverty reduction for national development in Nigeria was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results indicate that Entrepreneurship Education has a significant effect on job creation for national development. As shown in Table 1, the majority of respondents (132) agreed that entrepreneurship education has a significant effect on job creation. Since the calculated mean score of the respondents was 2.8 greater than the 2.5 bench mark for agreement, the researcher concluded that, respondents agreed with the notion that, entrepreneurship Education has significant effect on job creation for national development. The results in Table 4 further reveal that the effect of entrepreneurship education on job creation was statistically significant. Regression analysis indicated that, rcalculated (0.739) was greater than r-critical (0.088) at 0.05 level of significance ($p > 0.001$). This finding is in line with Kamar et al. (2021), who opined that entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in changing students' views towards becoming self-employed. This is because entrepreneurship education is meant to train students upon graduation to become self-reliant and employers of labor through creative and innovative thinking in identifying new business opportunities.

The study also found that Entrepreneurship Education had a significant impact on poverty reduction for national development, as shown in Table 2. Most respondents (129) agreed that entrepreneurship education has a significant impact on poverty reduction. Since the calculated mean score of the respondents was 2.7 greater than the 2.5 bench mark for agreement, the researchers concluded that entrepreneurship education had a significant impact on poverty reduction for national development. The results in Table 5 further reveal that the impact of entrepreneurship education on job creation was statistically significant. Regression analysis indicated that, r calculated (0.730) was greater than r-critical (0.088) at 0.05 level of significance ($p > 0.001$). This finding is in line with Ifeoma et al. (2018), who claimed that entrepreneurship development is a key tool for poverty reduction, stimulating employment, and economic growth in developing countries. Usman and Adam (2017) posit that a significant positive relationship exists between entrepreneurship and poverty reduction.

The study also revealed that the provision of funds by the government, financial institutions, and NGO's, the provision of interest-free loans to start up business, establishment of centers for entrepreneurship development, and provision of a conducive environment and facilities for teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education will enhance Entrepreneurship Education for national development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- I. Entrepreneurship Education has significant effect on job creation and poverty reduction for national development.
- II. Provision of funds by Government, financial institution and NGO's, provision of interest free loan to start up business, establishment of centers for Entrepreneurship development and provision of conducive environment and facilities for teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education will enhance Entrepreneurship Education for national development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made by the researchers;

- I. Center for entrepreneurship education should be established in every tertiary institution while undergraduate students should be mandated to go for internship skill acquisition.
- II. Government should increase the budgetary allocation and provide soft free interest loan to graduating students to start their businesses. In addition, the institutions should ensure the provision of appropriate instructional materials and equipment for job creation and poverty reduction for national development.

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